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Mathematics Expert in Data Analytics and Machine Learning
Thesis

**AUTOMATED THEOREM PROVING AND MACHINE
LEARNING**

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A **diplomamunka** szerzőjeként fegyelmi felelősségem tudatában kijelentem, hogy a dolgozatom önálló szellemi alkotásom, abban a hivatkozások és idézések standard szabályait következetesen alkalmaztam, mások által írt részeket a megfelelő idézés nélkül nem használtam fel.

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1. Introduction

Theoretically, automatic theorem proving (ATP) [10] can be used to attempt the proof of any formally stated provable mathematical conjecture. Traditional approaches usually rely on fast implementation of manually designed search procedures and heuristics. However, ATP systems implementing these methods are still weaker than trained mathematicians in various research domains.

Using statistical machine learning to guide the prover in selecting the next inference step during the proving process can significantly increase the performance compared to unguided systems.

In this thesis, we present a framework for ATP called plCoP, which builds on the leanCoP Prolog implementation and adds machine learning-guided Monte Carlo Tree Search.

Additionally, we present a graph neural network (GNN) model that embeds mathematical clauses, formulas, and proof states in a way that remains invariant to the renaming of variables, functions, and predicate symbols, as well as under negation and reordering of clauses and literals. This model can then be used to guide the inference steps during proof search.

The structure of this thesis is as follows: In Section 2, we present the plCoP system and we show how the proving process is interleaved with machine learning training steps. In Section 3, we describe a hypergraph model for property invariant embeddings. In Section 4, we briefly introduce the ManyProofs project, which explores handling multiple proof branches simultaneously for better generalization performance. We also describe our experiments and evaluate the performance of different models. Finally, in Section 5, we conclude with a summary of the thesis and propose some ideas for future work.

My main contribution to this thesis was implementing the hypergraph model described in Section 3 using PyTorch and integrating it into plCoP. I also ran experiments with this model in the ManyProofs project. These experiments showed that with each iteration of data collection and training, the model can solve an increasing number of problems from the given set of statements. However, the implementation currently only works well with small datasets and needs more optimization and parallelization for larger datasets.

While my work builds on various research articles, detailed references will be provided in their respective sections. The plCoP framework, including my contributions, is available on GitHub at https://github.com/zsoltzombori/leancop_ml. Please note that the `manyproofs` branch is currently private and may be merged into the master branch or made public in the future.

2. Reinforcement Learning and Theorem Proving

In this section, we present the Prolog-based automated theorem prover called plCoP [2], which builds on the leanCoP implementation and adds machine learning-guided Monte Carlo Tree Search to guide its connection tableau-style proof search. leanCoP [5, 6] is a compact automated theorem prover for classical first-order logic, implementing connection tableau search [11]. Other components of plCoP include a Python interface between plCoP and machine learning models, and an external proof checker, that verifies the validity of the resulting plCoP proofs. In the following subsections, we provide a detailed description of the main components and inner workflow of plCoP based on [2, 3, 1].

2.1. Basic First-Order Logic Terminology

Before we start discussing the details of plCoP, let's introduce some definitions from first-order logic that we will need later. This section is based on the first chapter of [9].

Definition 2.1 (Term). A Term is defined by the following recursion:

- Variables and constants (functions with 0 arity) are terms.
- If t_1, \dots, t_n are terms and f is a function with arity n , then $f(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ is also a term.

Definition 2.2 (Atomic formula). An Atomic Formula is defined as follows:

- If t_1, \dots, t_n are terms and P is a predicate with arity n , then $P(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ is an atomic formula.
- If t_1 and t_2 are terms, then $t_1 = t_2$ is an atomic formula.

Definition 2.3 (Literal). A Literal is an atomic formula or its negation.

Definition 2.4 (Clause). A Clause is a finite disjunction of literals.

Definition 2.5 (Clausal Normal Form). A first-order logic formula is in conjunctive normal form or clause normal form if it is a conjunction of one or more clauses.

In the logical language, the constants, variables, function symbols, and predicate symbols collectively form the 'signature' of the language. We assume these as inputs to the automatic theorem proving process, and the definitions here explain how expressions can be constructed from these elements.

2.2. Connection Tableau-Style Theorem Proving

First, we describe the connection tableau-style theorem proving process as implemented in leanCoP.

As an input, we start with a mathematical problem consisting of axioms and a conjecture formally stated in first-order logic. These first-order formulas are first translated to clause normal form, producing a set of first-order clauses.

The first step in the proof process is to negate the conjecture. Then, the calculus searches for refutational proofs, i.e., proofs showing that the axioms together with the negated conjecture are unsatisfiable.

The proof starts with a start clause as a goal and proceeds by building a connection tableau, i.e., a tree by iteratively applying extension steps and reduction steps to it.

- An extension step connects (unifies) the current goal (a selected leaf of a tableau branch) with a complementary literal from a new instance of an input clause. This step extends the current branch, possibly splitting it into several other branches if there are more literals in the axiom and possibly instantiating some variables in the tableau.
- A reduction step connects the current goal to a complementary literal of the active path, closing the current branch. The proof is finished when all branches are closed.

These extension and reduction steps are nondeterministic, requiring backtracking in the standard connection calculus. The iterative deepening search algorithm is typically used to ensure completeness, making sure the proof search finds a proof if there is any. In plCoP, iterative deepening is replaced with learning-guided Monte Carlo Tree Search.

Using the extension and reduction steps, we can achieve a closed connection tableau with the following properties:

- The root of the tree is an instance of the given start clause.
- The children of every non-leaf node are instances of an axiom. Moreover, one of the child literals must be complementary to the parent node.
- Every leaf node is complementary to an element of its path.

An example set of clauses (c_1 (negated) conjecture, $c_2 - c_6$ axioms) and a closed connection tableau are shown in Figure 1.

Clauses:

$$c_1 : P(x) = \neg \text{Conj}(x)$$

$$c_2 : R(x, y) \vee \neg P(x) \vee Q(y)$$

$$c_3 : S(x) \vee \neg Q(b)$$

$$c_4 : \neg S(x) \vee \neg Q(x)$$

$$c_5 : \neg Q(x) \vee \neg R(a, x)$$

$$c_6 : \neg R(a, x) \vee Q(x)$$

Tableau:

Figure 1: Closed connection tableau for a set of clauses (adapted from [1]).

Considering the above (nondeterministic) algorithm, in each step the only decisions that have to be made are "which axiom should be used for which node"? leanCoP starts with the initial clause and in each step it selects the left-most unclosed leaf. If the leaf can be unified with an element in the active path, the reduction step is applied. Otherwise, an extension step is performed and a decision on which literal in which axiom should be used has to be made, and the leaf has to be unified with the selected literal from the axiom.

The process continues until the entire tree is closed (the prover wins), or there are no remaining steps available (the prover loses). As most branches are infinite, usually additional limits are introduced, and the prover also loses if these limits are reached.

2.3. Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning [14] aims to find the optimal behaviour in an environment defined as a Markov Decision Process. A Markov Decision Process, denoted by the tuple $\text{MDP}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{P}, \gamma)$, describes a dynamic process and consists of the following components:

- \mathcal{S} is the set of possible states.
- \mathcal{A} is the set of possible actions.
- $\mathcal{R} : (\mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R})$ is the reward function.
- $\mathcal{P} : (\mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{S})$ is the state transition function.
- γ is the discount factor.

We assume that an agent interacts with this MDP, generating sequences of (s_t, a_t, r_t) state-action-reward tuples, called trajectories. The agent is equipped with a policy function $\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$, which determines which action it selects in a particular state. The policy is often stochastic, defining a probability distribution over inferences that are possible in a given state.

The aim of the agent is to maximize its total accumulated reward $\sum_{t \geq 0} \gamma^t r_t$, where future rewards are discounted with the γ discount factor. Several components, such as the reward and transition functions, can be stochastic. In this case, the agent's aim is to find the policy π^* that maximizes its cumulative expected reward:

$$\pi^* = \arg \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t \geq 0} \gamma^t r_t \mid \pi \right].$$

In the context of theorem proving, the reinforcement learning environment consists of the current proof state, actions correspond to proof steps, and the reward signals indicate the success or failure of proof attempts.

Monte Carlo Tree Search, described in the next subsection, can also be enhanced with reinforcement learning by using value functions and policies learned through RL to guide the search process. The value function estimates the expected reward from a given proof state, while the policy suggests the most promising actions to take.

2.4. Monte Carlo Tree Search

As mentioned above, in plCoP iterative deepening is removed, and Monte Carlo Tree Search is used instead to select the next action (axiom) when guiding the proof search [12].

Monte Carlo Tree Search [13] is a search algorithm for sequential decision processes that has been successfully used with reinforcement learning for action selection and state evaluation to achieve superhuman performance in games like Go (AlphaGo [7], AlphaZero [8]).

MCTS builds a tree whose nodes are states of the process, and edges represent sequential decisions. Each state (node) yields some reward. The aim of the algorithm is to find branches in the search tree that yield high accumulated rewards. The search starts from a single root node (starting state), and new nodes are added iteratively. In each node i , we maintain the number of visits n_i , the total reward r_i , and its prior probability p_i given by a learned policy function. Each iteration, also called playout, starts with the addition of a new leaf node. This is done by recursively selecting a child that maximizes the standard UCT formula (2.1) [15], until a leaf is found. In (2.1), N is the number of visits of the parent, and cp is a parameter that determines the balance between nodes with high value (exploitation) and rarely visited nodes (exploration). Each leaf is given an initial value, which is typically provided by a learned value function. Next, parents are updated: Visit counts are increased by 1, and value estimates are increased by the value of the newly added node. The value and policy functions are learned in AlphaGo/AlphaZero and in plCoP.

$$UCT(i) = \frac{r_i}{n_i} + cp \cdot p_i \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln N}{n_i}} \quad (2.1)$$

2.5. MCTS with Connection Tableau Theorem Proving

We now describe how Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) is used to guide the inference steps when combined with a connection tableau-style theorem prover.

plCoP uses the DAgger [16] meta-learning algorithm to learn the policy and value functions. DAgger interleaves automatic theorem proving runs with a training phase, in

which an (arbitrary) machine learning model is trained using reinforcement learning to predict values and policies from given proof states.

The algorithm runs as follows:

1. In Stage 0, there is no machine learning guidance for the automated theorem prover. During this stage, a Monte Carlo Search Tree is built for each training problem, and the training data based on the proof states are collected and saved.
2. From Stage 1 onwards, before rebuilding the MCTS trees for each of the training problems and re-collecting the training data, we interleave the automatic theorem proving with training a machine learning model using the saved training data from the previous stage. This model is then used to guide the tree search by predicting values and policies.

During the proof search, when plCoP builds the Monte Carlo Tree for each training problem, the tree's nodes represent the entire current proof state (partial tableau), and the edges of the tree represent the proof inferences. Note that the Monte Carlo Tree is different from the connection tableau trees. A branch of the Monte Carlo Tree leading to a node with a closed tableau represents a valid proof.

Initially (in Stage 0), plCoP uses simple heuristic value and policy functions, which are later replaced with the learned guidance from the model. In guiding the prover, various Python machine learning models can be used, which are called by the Prolog prover through the Python API. Typically, decisions need to be made on the Prolog side regarding which training data should be saved from a given proof state and in what format, so that the Python model can use it.

To enforce deeper exploration, after a fixed number of playouts, we perform a bigstep: the starting node of exploration is moved one level down towards the child with the highest value (called the bigstep node). Later MCTS steps only extend the subtree under the bigstep node. This in practice means there is no backtracking of the bigsteps, which, in turn, involves giving up completeness.

3. A Hypergraph Model for Property Invariant Embeddings

In this section, we present a hypergraph neural network model that we will later use to guide the prover.

The proposed model has several useful invariance properties: it remains invariant not only under the renaming of variables, but also under the renaming of arbitrary function and predicate symbols. Additionally, it is invariant under the negation of symbols and the reordering of clauses and literals.

These invariance properties are important during the proof search, where typically many new, problem specific, and previously unseen variables, function, and predicate symbols are introduced during the clausification of the input formulas and instantiation of the axioms in the inference steps. These new variables, function and predicate symbols can also appear multiple times in the given formula.

With the hypergraph model, we embed the formulas in such a way that it represents symbols only by nodes in the graph, without giving the network any knowledge of the original labels. We provide additional links between these nodes that allow the network to recover the meaning and correctly embed the nodes irrespective of the given labels.

First, we describe the construction of the hypergraph structure, the storage of training data within the hypergraph and the embedding of the node data into vectors of real numbers.

Next, we describe the graph convolution with message passing layers based on the node embeddings and edges of the hypergraph.

Finally, we present the complete neural network model. This includes the embedding of the graph's nodes into vectors of real numbers, passing these embeddings through the message passing layers, and then using fully connected layers with ReLU and sigmoid activation functions to output the final predicted values and policies.

In the last subsection we present a proof of the invariance properties of the network.

This section is based entirely on [4].

3.1. Construction of the Hypergraph

To construct the hypergraph, we need to convert the current proof state into a graph representation, ensuring that we capture as much relevant structure as possible during the process.

The actual proof state can be described with a set of clauses $\mathbf{C} = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{n_c}\}$, where n_c denotes the number of clauses.

Similarly, let $\mathbf{T} = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_{n_t}\}$ denote all the literals and subterms occurring at least once in the above set of clauses, and let $\mathbf{S} = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{n_s}\}$ denote all the function and predicate symbols occurring at least once in the given set of clauses. These sets, \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{S} will form the nodes of the hypergraph.

In \mathbf{T} , two subterms are considered identical and represented only by a single node if they are constructed the same way using the same functions and variables. Also, if T_i is a negative literal, the unnegated form of T_i is not automatically added to \mathbf{T} , but all of its subterms are.

The hypergraph will have two different kinds of edges:

1. Between clauses and literals, we have the edges $\mathbf{E}_{ct} \subset \mathbf{C} \times \mathbf{T}$. The set \mathbf{E}_{ct} contains all the pairs (C_i, T_j) , where T_j is a literal contained in C_i . Note that due to this encoding, the order of the literals in the clauses is irrelevant, which is exactly what we want to achieve.
2. Between symbols and terms, we have 4-ary oriented labeled edges in the following form: $\mathbf{E}_{st} \subset \mathbf{S} \times \mathbf{T} \times (\mathbf{T} \cup \{T_0\})^2 \times \{1, -1\}$. This set contains tuples (S_i, T_j, T_k, T_l, d) , where:
 - S_i is a function or predicate symbol.
 - T_j is a term or literal in which S_i appears.
 - T_k and T_l are subterms or T_0 (a special term node disjoint from all other terms indicating absence of a subterm, used in the arity-related encodings).
 - d is a direction indicator, where 1 and -1 indicate different orientations of the edge.

The set \mathbf{E}_{st} is constructed as follows. For every literal or subterm T_i that is not a variable:

- If T_i is a negative literal, we set $d = 1$ and interpret T_i as $T_i = \neg S_j(t_1, \dots, t_n)$.
- If T_i is a positive literal, we set $d = -1$ and interpret T_i as $T_i = S_j(t_1, \dots, t_n)$.

Here, $S_j \in \mathbf{S}$, n is the arity of S_j , and $t_1, \dots, t_n \in \mathbf{T}$. Then:

- If $n = 0$, we add (S_j, T_i, T_0, T_0, d) to \mathbf{E}_{st} .
- If $n = 1$, we add (S_j, T_i, t_1, T_0, d) to \mathbf{E}_{st} .
- If $n \geq 2$, we add all $(S_j, T_i, t_k, t_{k+1}, d)$ to \mathbf{E}_{st} for $k = 1, \dots, n - 1$.

We use this encoding instead of just (S_j, T_i, t_k, d) to maintain the order of the function and predicate arguments. Note, that even this encoding does not capture the complete information about the argument order. For example, the encoding is the same for $f(t_1, t_2, t_1)$ and $f(t_2, t_1, t_2)$.

3.2. Embedding of the Graph's Nodes into Real Vectors

After constructing the hypergraph from the current proof state, we need to embed the node data into real vectors as initial inputs for the message passing layers in the graph convolution.

The data that will be embedded consists of labels of nonnegative integers, which are assigned to the nodes of the hypergraph based on the "type" of clause, symbol, or term the nodes represent.

Types of Clauses, Symbols and Terms

The labels are assigned as follows:

- (Types of Clauses) As mentioned before, to construct the hypergraph, we convert the current proof state into a graph representation, described by a set of clauses $\mathbf{C} = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{n_c}\}$. This set \mathbf{C} includes:

- A axioms
- A path of length P in the actual proof state
- The current goal clause
- Clauses representing unfinished goals in the current path and earlier branches

Therefore, clauses can be of four types:

- The current goal (0)
- An unfinished goal (1)
- A clause from the current path (2)
- A clause from an axiom (3)

These clauses roughly correspond to the clauses from which we aim to obtain the contradiction in the proof. Each of these clause node labels is embedded into learnable vectors of dimension 4.

- (Types of Symbols) Symbols can be either functions or predicates, so their types are:
 - Function (0)
 - Predicate (1)

Symbol node labels are embedded into vectors of dimension 1 (a single real number), with 0 for predicates and a learnable real number for functions. Predicate symbols are initialized to the zero vector to preserve invariance under negation.

- (Types of Terms) For term nodes, variables in different axioms are always considered to be different, and they are also considered to be different from the variables in the tableau, as the extension step in the proof process performs variable renaming and introduces new variables. Variables in the tableau are shared among the path and the goals. Term nodes can be of four types:
 - A literal ($L = P(t_1, \dots, t_n)$, where P is a predicate) (0)

- Another term ($T = f(t_1, \dots, t_n)$, where f is a function, as terms are defined recursively) (1)
- A variable in the tableau (2)
- A variable in an axiom (3)

Term node labels are embedded into learnable vectors of dimension 4.

Embedding Process

The result of the embedding process will be vectors $c_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, $s_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^1$, and $t_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^4$ for each type of clause, symbol, and term, respectively.

For example, if we have five different clauses with the initial node labels $\mathbf{X}_C = [0, 1, 3, 3, 3]$, the embedding will result in a 5×4 matrix where each row is a vector of dimension 4: $c_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^4$ for $j = 1, \dots, 5$. The last three rows will be the same because the initial node labels are the same for them. The embedding is done similarly for symbols and terms.

3.3. Graph Convolution with Message Passing Layers

Once the initial embeddings are created for the node labels, resulting in the starting vectors $c_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, $s_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^1$, and $t_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, we propagate these vectors through L message passing layers. During this process, we construct the updated vectors $c_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_c^i}$, $s_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_s^i}$, and $t_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_t^i}$, where d_c^i , d_s^i and d_t^i are dimensions of the vectors in each layer for $i = 1, \dots, L$. The values of these dimensions, as well as the number of layers L , are hyperparameters that can be adjusted.

The i -th layer will take as input the vectors $c_{i-1,j}$, $s_{i-1,j}$, and $t_{i-1,j}$ from the previous layer and will output the updated vectors $c_{i,j}$, $s_{i,j}$, $t_{i,j}$. The output of the last layer, $c_{L,j}$, $s_{L,j}$, $t_{L,j}$, is considered the final output of the graph convolution.

The message passing layers for the hypergraph work similarly to message passing layers for standard graphs with graph convolutions. These layers iteratively update the node embeddings based on the nodes themselves and their neighbours connected by the edges in \mathbf{E}_{ct} and \mathbf{E}_{st} .

During these updates, we also consider the direction in which the information is passed. For example, when updating a clause vector, it receives information from the neighbouring term nodes, but when a term node is updated, the information is passed from neighbouring clauses and symbols to this term node. To the nodes from which the information originates we apply a reduction function defined below.

The symbol nodes $s_{i,j}$ require special attention, because they can represent two predicate symbols at once: if $s_{i,j}$ represents a predicate symbol P , then $-s_{i,j}$ represents the predicate symbol $\neg P$. To preserve invariance to negation, the symbol nodes are handled slightly differently.

The message passing process for each type of node can be described with the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{i+1,j} &= \text{ReLU}(B_{\mathbf{c}}^i + M_{\mathbf{c}}^i \cdot c_{i,j} + M_{\mathbf{ct}}^i \cdot \text{red}_{a \in F_{\mathbf{ct}}^j} (t_{i,a})) \\
x_i^{a,b,c} &= B_{\mathbf{ts}}^i + M_{\mathbf{ts},1}^i \cdot t_{i,a} + M_{\mathbf{ts},2}^i \cdot t_{i,b} + M_{\mathbf{ts},3}^i \cdot t_{i,c} \\
s_{i+1,j} &= \tanh(M_{\mathbf{s}}^i \cdot s_{i,j} + M_{\mathbf{ts}}^i \cdot \text{red}'_{(a,b,c,g) \in F_{\mathbf{st}}^j} (g \cdot x_i^{a,b,c})) \\
y_{i,d}^{a,b,c,g} &= B_{\mathbf{st}}^i + M_{\mathbf{st},i}^{1,d} \cdot t_{i,a} + M_{\mathbf{st},i}^{2,d} \cdot t_{i,b} + M_{\mathbf{st},i}^{3,d} \cdot s_{i,c} \cdot g \\
z_{i,j,d} &= M_{\mathbf{st},d}^i \cdot \text{red}_{(a,b,c,g) \in F_{\mathbf{ts},d}^j} (\text{ReLU}(y_{i,d}^{a,b,c,g})) \\
v_{i,j} &= M_{\mathbf{tc}}^i \cdot \text{red}_{a \in F_{\mathbf{tc}}^j} (c_{i,a}) \\
t_{i+1,j} &= \text{ReLU}(B_{\mathbf{t}}^i + M_{\mathbf{t}}^i \cdot t_{i,j} + v_{i,j} + \sum_{d \in \{1,2,3\}} z_{i,j,d})
\end{aligned}$$

Here, all the M symbols represent learnable matrices and all the B symbols represent learnable bias vectors. Essentially, the matrices M paired with the appropriate bias vectors B form fully connected layers. Their dimensions can be seen on Table 1.

The reduction operations used in the formulas are defined as follows:

Definition 3.1. For $u_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the operation $\text{red}_{i \in I}(u_i)$ is defined as a vector of dimension $2n$, where the first n coordinates are given by $\max_{i \in I}(u_i)$ and the second n coordinates by $\text{avg}_{i \in I}(u_i)$. Both the maximum and average operations are taken element-wise.

The reduction operation $\text{red}'_{i \in I}(u_i)$ is defined similarly to red , but instead of taking the maximum in the first n coordinates, we use $\max_{i \in I}(u_i) + \min_{i \in I}(u_i)$. This ensures that red' commutes with multiplication by -1 , as it is an odd function.

If a reduction operation receives an empty input (i.e., the index set is empty in the formulas), the result is the zero vector of the appropriate size.

Symbol	Dimensions
$B_{\mathbf{c}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{c}}^{i+1}$
$M_{\mathbf{c}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{c}}^{i+1} \times d_{\mathbf{c}}^i$
$M_{\mathbf{ct}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{c}}^{i+1} \times 2d_{\mathbf{t}}^i$
$B_{\mathbf{ts}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{s}}^{i+1}$
$M_{\mathbf{ts},1}^i, M_{\mathbf{ts},2}^i, M_{\mathbf{ts},3}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{s}}^{i+1} \times d_{\mathbf{t}}^i$
$M_{\mathbf{s}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{s}}^{i+1} \times d_{\mathbf{s}}^i$
$M_{\mathbf{ts}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{s}}^{i+1} \times 2d_{\mathbf{s}}^{i+1}$
$B_{\mathbf{st}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{t}}^{i+1}$
$M_{\mathbf{st},i}^{1,d}, M_{\mathbf{st},i}^{2,d}, M_{\mathbf{st},i}^{3,d}$	$d_{\mathbf{t}}^{i+1} \times d_{\mathbf{t}}^i$
$M_{\mathbf{st},d}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{t}}^{i+1} \times 2d_{\mathbf{t}}^{i+1}$
$M_{\mathbf{tc}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{t}}^{i+1} \times 2d_{\mathbf{c}}^i$
$B_{\mathbf{t}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{t}}^{i+1}$
$M_{\mathbf{t}}^i$	$d_{\mathbf{t}}^{i+1} \times d_{\mathbf{t}}^i$

Table 1: Dimensions of the learnable matrices and bias vectors.

The sets in the formulas $F_{\mathbf{ct}}^{j_{\mathbf{c}}}, F_{\mathbf{tc}}^{j_{\mathbf{t}}}, F_{\mathbf{st}}^{j_{\mathbf{s}}}, F_{\mathbf{ts},d}^{j_{\mathbf{t}}}$ are index sets defined based on the edges in the hypergraph for $j_{\mathbf{c}} = 1, \dots, n_{\mathbf{c}}, j_{\mathbf{t}} = 1, \dots, n_{\mathbf{t}}, j_{\mathbf{s}} = 1, \dots, n_{\mathbf{s}}$, and $d = 1, 2, 3$.

- $F_{\mathbf{ct}}^{j_{\mathbf{c}}}$ and $F_{\mathbf{tc}}^{j_{\mathbf{t}}}$ contain indices for clause-term edges in $E_{\mathbf{ct}}$.
- Similarly, $F_{\mathbf{st}}^{j_{\mathbf{s}}}$ and $F_{\mathbf{ts},d}^{j_{\mathbf{t}}}$ contain indices between symbol-term edges in $E_{\mathbf{st}}$.

These index sets are formally defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{\mathbf{ct}}^j &= \{a : (C_j, T_a) \in E_{\mathbf{ct}}\} \\
F_{\mathbf{tc}}^j &= \{a : (C_a, T_j) \in E_{\mathbf{ct}}\} \\
F_{\mathbf{st}}^j &= \{(a, b, c, g) : (S_j, T_a, T_b, T_c, g) \in E_{\mathbf{st}}\} \\
F_{\mathbf{ts},1}^j &= \{(a, b, c, g) : (S_c, T_j, T_a, T_b, g) \in E_{\mathbf{st}}\} \\
F_{\mathbf{ts},2}^j &= \{(a, b, c, g) : (S_c, T_a, T_j, T_b, g) \in E_{\mathbf{st}}\} \\
F_{\mathbf{ts},3}^j &= \{(a, b, c, g) : (S_c, T_a, T_b, T_j, g) \in E_{\mathbf{st}}\}
\end{aligned}$$

For any set $F_{\mathbf{xy}}^j$, it contains indices for all the neighbours of the j -th node for message passing, where the information is passed from a node of type \mathbf{y} to the j -th node of type \mathbf{x} . For example, $F_{\mathbf{ct}}^j$ contains all the indices for the neighbours of the j -th clause node when the message passing is done from the neighbouring term nodes to this j -th clause node.

As $E_{\mathbf{st}}$ can contain a dummy node T_0 on the third and fourth positions in the edge tuple, during message passing, a non-existent vector $t_{i,0}$ could be referenced from $F_{\mathbf{st}}^j$ or $F_{\mathbf{ts},d}^j$. In this case, we use the zero vector of dimension $d_{\mathbf{t}}^i$ as $t_{i,0}$.

This concludes the description of the message passing mechanism for the hypergraph convolution.

3.4. The Complete Model: From Input to Output

Now, we have all the components to present the complete model: from the initial embedding of the inputs, through the message passing layers, to predicting the final values and policies that guide the theorem proving process.

1. First, the model receives as input the constructed hypergraph representing the current proof state, as described in Subsection 3.1.
2. Next, the initial node labels are embedded to vectors of real numbers: $c_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, $s_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^1$, and $t_{0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, based on the types of the nodes, as described in Subsection 3.2.
3. Then, these initial embeddings are propagated through five message passing layers with dimensions $d_{\mathbf{c}}^i = d_{\mathbf{t}}^i = 32$ and $d_{\mathbf{s}}^i = 64$ for $i = 1, \dots, 5$ to obtain $c_{5,j}$, $t_{5,j}$, $s_{5,j}$ as explained in Subsection 3.3.

4. To compute the final predicted value, we take all the $c_{5,j}$ vectors, apply a hidden layer of size 64 with ReLU activation, apply the red reduction function, and use one more hidden layer of size 64 with ReLU activation. Finally, to predict the value, we use a fully connected layer that maps to a single dimension with sigmoid activation.
5. To compute the final predicted action logits for actions that correspond to the use of axiom C_i , complementing its literal T_j with the current goal, we use the following layers. Let C_k represent the clause for all the remaining goals. Then, we concatenate $c_{5,i}$, $t_{5,j}$, and $c_{5,k}$, process this concatenated vector with a hidden layer of size 64 with ReLU activation, and use a fully connected output layer without an activation function.

3.5. Proof of the Invariance Properties of the Hypergraph Network

Now, we present the proof of the invariance properties of the network, namely that it remains invariant not only under the renaming of variables, but also under the renaming of arbitrary function and predicate symbols, under the reordering of clauses and literals, and additionally preserves the symmetry under negation.

Invariance Under Renaming of Variables and Symbols

The network must be invariant to the renaming of both variables and function/predicate symbols. This invariance is achieved because the initial embeddings are determined by the types of the nodes (clauses, terms, symbols) rather than their specific names. The message passing mechanism relies on these embeddings and the structure of the hypergraph, not on the actual names of the symbols.

When constructing the hypergraph, the names are only used to determine which symbol nodes and term nodes should be the same and which should be different. For example, if a variable x is renamed to y or a function symbol f is renamed to g , the corresponding embeddings and the hypergraph structure remain the same. Therefore, the messages passed during the convolution process remain unchanged because the network does not

directly reference the names of the symbols but instead operates on the embeddings associated with these nodes. Consequently, the final output of the network is also invariant to the renaming.

Invariance Under Reordering of Clauses and Literals

The network also needs to be invariant to the reordering of clauses and literals within the clauses. This property is ensured by the structure of the hypergraph and the message passing mechanism. When clauses or literals are reordered, the edges and adjacency relationships in the hypergraph remain unchanged, as there is no ordered processing of the data and the graph edges are also unordered. This means the propagation of information through the network remains the same.

If we reorder the clauses C_1, \dots, C_{n_c} , the values $c_{i,1}, \dots, c_{i,n_c}$ are reordered the same way. While $s_{i,j}, t_{i,j}$ could be reordered in general, they do not change if they still correspond to the same symbols and terms. Formally, let π be a permutation of clauses or literals. Then:

$$c_{i+1,\pi(j)} = \text{ReLU}(B_{\mathbf{c}}^i + M_{\mathbf{c}}^i \cdot c_{i,\pi(j)} + M_{\mathbf{ct}}^i \cdot \text{red}_{a \in F_{\mathbf{ct}}^{\pi(j)}}(t_{i,a})).$$

Due to the commutativity of the reduction functions and that π only reorders indices, the resulting embeddings are invariant to these permutations.

Symmetry Under Negation

The network also needs to be symmetric under the negation of symbols.

Claim 3.1. *If every occurrence of the predicate symbol S_x is replaced with the predicate symbol $\neg S_x$ in every clause C_i and every literal T_i , then the vectors $c_{i,j}$ and $t_{i,j}$ do not change, and the vectors $s_{i,j}$ do not change for $j \neq x$, but $s_{i,x}$ is multiplied by -1 .*

Proof. We prove this claim by induction on the layer i .

On layer 0, as S_x is a predicate symbol, by construction $s_{0,x} = \mathbf{0} = -s_{0,x} \in \mathbb{R}^1$.

Assume the claim is true for layer i . We show that it also holds for layer $i + 1$.

- When computing $c_{i+1,j}$, the symbols vectors $s_{i,j}$ are not used in the message passing formula, so $c_{i+1,j}$ remains the same.
- When computing $t_{i+1,j}$, all $s_{i,c}$ are multiplied by the appropriate g sign in the message passing formula. As S_x is replaced by $\neg S_x$ and all other symbols are unchanged, by construction of the hypergraph edges the sign g is multiplied by -1 if and only if $c = x$. By the induction hypothesis $s_{i,x}$ is also multiplied by -1 , so in the message passing formula we have $(-1) \cdot s_{i,x} \cdot (-1) \cdot g = s_{i,x} \cdot g$, therefore the product remains the same and $t_{i+1,j}$ does not change.
- When computing $s_{i+1,j}$ for $j \neq x$, the symbols vector $s_{i,x}$ is not used in the message passing formula and the g signs remain the same in $F_{\mathbf{st}}^j$. Therefore, $s_{i+1,j}$ remains the same.
- Finally, when computing $s_{i+1,x}$, we have the following in the message passing formula:

$$s_{i+1,x} = \tanh(M_{\mathbf{s}}^i \cdot s_{i,x} + M_{\mathbf{ts}}^i \cdot \text{red}'_{(a,b,c,g) \in F_{\mathbf{st}}^x} (g \cdot x_i^{a,b,c})).$$

Here, $x_i^{a,b,c}$ depends only on the values of $t_{i,j}$, which are unchanged. On the other hand, we can rewrite this formula as:

$$s_{i+1,x} = -\tanh(M_{\mathbf{s}}^i \cdot (-s_{i,x}) + M_{\mathbf{ts}}^i \cdot \text{red}'_{(a,b,c,g) \in F_{\mathbf{st}}^x} ((-g) \cdot x_i^{a,b,c})).$$

This is valid because \tanh is an odd function ($\tanh(-x) = -\tanh(x)$), and the operations inside the argument of \tanh (addition, matrix multiplication and red') are compatible with multiplication by -1 .

In the second formula $-s_{i,x}$ (by induction) and $-g$ (by construction) are the original values of $s_{i,x}$ and g before replacing S_x with $\neg S_x$. Therefore, the right hand side of the second formula is equivalent to the original formula multiplied by -1 , so $s_{i+1,x}$ was indeed multiplied by -1 . This concludes the proof of the invariance properties of the network.

□

4. Experiment and Evaluation

In this chapter, we introduce the ManyProofs project, present a baseline model for ManyProofs, describe the specifics of our experimental setup, and present the results of the prover guided by both the baseline model and the hypergraph model.

4.1. ManyProofs

ManyProofs is an ongoing research project that explores a fundamental challenge in learning from theorem proving attempts. The main problems are the weakly labeled training signals in two different ways. First, many possible proof derivations are never explored, so their value remains unknown. Second, even among the explored derivations, multiple paths may lead to proofs, but we do not know which ones generalize well to other problems. This latter challenge, known as the problem of disjunctive supervision, is discussed in the article "Towards Unbiased Exploration in Partial Label Learning" [17].

Theorem proving provides an interesting application area for the methods and results discussed in that paper, and a core ambition of the ManyProofs project is to see how well those results hold in the context of theorem proving. Instead of making arbitrary choices about which proofs to learn from, we are experimenting with ways to learn from all proofs and letting the learning algorithm decide which ones to favor.

To explore these ideas in pCoP, we extract full proof derivation branches from the Prolog side when saving the training data for the guidance machine learning models, rather than saving only the current proof state. During the training of these models, we consider different loss functions to select the most favorable ones based on their generalization performance.

4.2. A Baseline Model

The baseline model, referred to as "SmallModel" in the implementation, consists of the following layers:

First, on its input joint layer, its inputs are transformed to the hidden layer's dimension size of 100, followed by a ReLU activation, Dropout layer with a dropout probability of

0.3, and a LayerNorm layer with the hidden dimension size.

Next, the same is repeated on the hidden joint layer, with a linear layer, ReLU activation, Dropout, and LayerNorm.

Then, to calculate the output values, we pass the result of the previous joint layers through a linear layer with dimension 100 followed by ReLU activation, then again a linear output layer that reduces the dimension to size 1 (the value output), followed by Sigmoid activation.

To calculate the policies, we again take the result of the previous joint layers, pass through a linear layer with dimension 100 with ReLU activation, and finally a last linear output layer that reduces the dimension to size 1 without activation.

The main layers of the baseline model can be summarized as follows:

- **Input Joint Layer:**

- Linear layer (input dimension to 100)
- ReLU activation
- Dropout (probability 0.3)
- LayerNorm (dimension 100)

- **Hidden Joint Layer:**

- Linear layer (100 to 100)
- ReLU activation
- Dropout (probability 0.3)
- LayerNorm (dimension 100)

- **Value Output:**

- Linear layer (100 to 100)
- ReLU activation
- Linear output layer (100 to 1)
- Sigmoid activation

- **Policy Output:**

- Linear layer (100 to 100)
- ReLU activation
- Linear output layer (100 to 1)

4.3. Experiment Setup

To run our experiments, we are working with plCoP in the `manyproofs` branch. We perform different numbers of training data collection and learning iterations during the experiments described later. As mentioned earlier, in iteration 0, there is only training data collection and saving on the Prolog side. From Stage 1 onwards, a new model is built based on the saved training data from the previous stage. This model is then used to guide the inference steps in the next Monte Carlo Tree Search phase, and the new training data will be saved based on this.

In Stage 0, the Monte Carlo Tree Search works randomly, but in later stages, it is guided by the learned value and policy guidance.

To evaluate the system, we are using the M2k dataset [18], which consists of 2003 Mizar40 problems. The Mizar40 dataset [19] consists of 32542 problems that come from related Mizar articles from the Mizar Mathematical Library [20].

We are training for a maximum of 100 epochs with early stopping after 20 epochs of no improvement on a separate validation set (split is by problems).

The evaluations are based on the different loss functions that were introduced in [17].

4.4. Evaluation of the Models

SmallModel

Loss	0	1	2	3	4	5
FREQS	548	779	863	877	895	910
NLL pos-s	548	770	849	887	923	922
NLL pos-r	548	763	891	926	932	973
NLL pos-s neg-s	548	753	857	904	915	916
NLL pos-r neg-r	548	707	830	872	887	907
NLL pos-l neg-l	548	779	879	881	913	949
NLL pos-a	548	500	813	870	907	941
NLL pos-a neg-a	548	761	832	885	925	949
UNIFORM pos-a	548	775	847	884	905	887
SAG	548	777	835	898	921	907
LIBRA	548	789	865	939	980	991
MERIT	548	771	872	921	943	977

Table 2: Number of problems solved on the M2k dataset with the SmallModel for various iterations and loss functions. Best models are marked with **boldface**.

We can see from the results that among the loss functions, the LIBRA model shows the best performance, solving 991 problems at iteration 5 and showing better performance than using all other loss functions in almost every iteration.

Hypergraph Model

We also tried to evaluate the performance of the hypergraph model on the ManyProofs framework to see how it performs compared to the baseline SmallModel. However, we encountered significant performance issues during testing.

First, during development, we tested the learning phase with a dummy dataset containing 7 problems to verify that the model works. One learning phase took approximately

10 minutes, which was already quite slow.

Next, we tested the model on the m2n140 dataset, which contains 131 problems. Here, one training phase took 25 hours to finish. Even though it took a long time, we confirmed that the model was learning, as it solved the same number of problems (43) as the SmallModel on this dataset. However, because of the learning phase took so long, we couldn't test it on the even larger M2k dataset to compare the actual performance of the hypergraph model with SmallModel.

From these tests, we see that the hypergraph model still needs further optimization and parallelization for handling larger datasets efficiently. Currently, the model operates by loading hypergraphs from proof states one by one. The next step would be to extend the model to load batches of hypergraphs simultaneously and exploit memory more effectively during training.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

In summary, our study explored automated theorem proving within the plCoP framework, leveraging reinforcement learning and Monte Carlo tree search techniques. We introduced the state-of-the-art hypergraph model from [4], which we implemented in PyTorch and integrated into plCoP. We focused more on explaining how the model works mathematically rather than getting into the technical details of the PyTorch implementation, which is available in the repository.

Additionally, we introduced the ManyProofs project, which aims to determine which proofs perform best in terms of generalization performance on other unseen problems based on different loss functions. We conducted experiments comparing the hypergraph model with the baseline SmallModel in plCoP in relation to the ManyProofs project. While the SmallModel demonstrated promising results, the hypergraph model encountered significant performance issues, indicating the need for further optimization and parallelization. However, if we solve these performance issues, we expect that the hypergraph model will show superior performance compared to the SmallModel.

So, based on this, the next step should definitely be to work further on the hypergraph model, focusing on optimization and parallelization to unlock its full potential and enhance automated theorem proving within the plCoP framework.

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